

AdaBoost-Based Channel Estimation in One-Bit Millimeter-Wave MIMO

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Abstract—Leveraging one-bit analog-to-digital converter (ADC) instead of high resolution ADC has been introduced as a promising solution for reducing the power consumption and hardware cost of massive millimeter-wave (mmWave) multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) systems. However, performance loss caused by discarding the amplitude information by one-bit quantizers is a significant impairment which calls for the development of more accurate channel estimators. To address this problem, a one-bit mmWave MIMO channel estimation method based on adaptive boosting (AdaBoost) which employs two-stage weak classifiers is developed. In the first stage of each weak classifier, an approximate Gaussian discriminant analysis (GDA) binary classifier is used. To capture the sparsity of mmWave channels in the angular domain, a hard thresholding operator is employed in the second stage of each weak classifier. Numerical simulations are included to demonstrate the efficiency and accuracy of the proposed channel estimator.

Index Terms—One-bit ADC, millimeter-wave, channel estimation, AdaBoost

I. INTRODUCTION

Leveraging millimeter-wave (mmWave) multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) communication systems enables high data rates and multi-user operation [1]–[4]. Two significant challenges in such communication systems rise because of the use of large number of antennas at base station (BS): high power consumption and hardware cost. This is a particularly severe problem when high-resolution analog-to-digital converter (ADC) and/or digital-to-analog converter (DAC) are employed for all antennas. To tackle these problems, low-resolution ADCs/DACs (1-3 bits) have been introduced as a feasible solution [5]–[15]. Particularly, power consumption can be significantly reduced by using one-bit ADCs/DACs. However, one-bit converters introduce a nonlinear operator to the signal model which necessitates the design of new channel estimators and data detectors.

Channel estimation and/or data detection for one-bit massive MIMO or mmWave MIMO systems have been extensively studied. A near maximum-likelihood (nML) approach has been developed in [10] for channel estimation and data detection in massive MIMO systems. The authors of [11] have exploited the Busgang decomposition [17] to propose Busgang linear minimum mean squared error (BLMMSE) channel estimators and data detectors. One-bit channel estimation and data detection problems have been formulated as binary classification problem in several papers such as [13], [15]. In [13], support vector machine (SVM)-based algorithms have been presented for one-bit channel estimation and data detection problems. In

[15], sparsity in the angular domain with logistic regression was combined in a channel estimator referred to as ℓ_1 regularized logistic regression with Toeplitz matrix reconstruction (L1-RLR-TMR) for one-bit mmWave systems.

Accuracy and computational efficiency are crucial in one-bit mmWave channel estimation, especially when there are large number of unknowns. However, the existing one-bit mmWave channel estimators may fail in satisfying these requirements. The goal of this work is to develop an efficient and accurate one-bit mmWave channel estimator by enforcing the sparse structure of mmWave channels embedded in a proper binary classification method. We develop an adaptive boosting (AdaBoost)-based channel estimation algorithm for one-bit mmWave MIMO systems. AdaBoost-based algorithms for one-bit channel estimation and data detection were first developed in [16]. Compared to [16], the focus of this work is on capturing the sparsity of one-bit mmWave MIMO channels in the angular domain using the AdaBoost framework. In doing so, a two-stage weak classifier is used in each iteration of AdaBoost. An approximate Gaussian discriminant analysis (GDA)-based binary classification is used in the first stage. A hard thresholding operator is employed as the second stage to enforce sparsity of the channel in the angular domain. The proposed channel estimator captures the actual sparsity level without prior knowledge. Numerical simulations are used to demonstrate the excellent performance of the proposed AdaBoost-based algorithm.

Notation: The transpose, and Hermitian transpose are denoted by $\{\cdot\}^T$ and $\{\cdot\}^H$, respectively. The $n \times n$ identity matrix is represented by \mathbf{I}_n . The operator $\text{vec}\{\cdot\}$ stacks the columns of a matrix into a column vector. The Kronecker product is denoted by \otimes , and $\Re\{\cdot\}$ and $\Im\{\cdot\}$ return the real and imaginary components of the bracketed argument, respectively. The notation $\mathcal{Q}(\cdot) \triangleq \text{sign}(\Re\{\cdot\}) + j\text{sign}(\Im\{\cdot\})$ stands for the element-wise one-bit quantizer, while $\mathbf{1}(\cdot)$ represents the indicator function. Finally, $\text{round}\{\cdot\}$ finds the closest integer to the bracketed scalar argument.

II. PROBLEM FORMULATION AND PRELIMINARIES

A. Observation Model

We consider an uplink (UL) multi-user mmWave system with K single-antenna users and a BS which deploys a uniform linear array (ULA) of M antenna elements. Each antenna element in the BS utilizes two one-bit ADCs for quantizing

the real and imaginary components of the received signals, while all users utilize high-resolution DACs. The UL channel between BS and the k^{th} user is modeled [8]:

$$\mathbf{h}_k = \sum_{l=1}^{L_k} \sum_{m=1}^{M_{\text{path}}^{k,l}} \gamma_{k,l,m} \mathbf{a}(\theta_{k,l,m}) = \mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_k) \boldsymbol{\gamma}_k \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{h}_k \in \mathbb{C}^M$, L_k is the number of multipath clusters, $M_{\text{path}}^{k,l}$ is the number of paths within the l^{th} multipath cluster, $\gamma_{k,l,m}$ and $\theta_{k,l,m}$ are the gain and direction-of-arrival (DOA) associated with the m^{th} path in the l^{th} multipath cluster, respectively. Additionally, $\mathbf{a}(\theta_{k,l,m}) = [1, e^{-j\pi \sin(\theta_{k,l,m})}, \dots, e^{-j(M-1)\pi \sin(\theta_{k,l,m})}]^T \in \mathbb{C}^M$ denotes the array steering vector at the BS for signal received from the direction $\theta_{k,l,m}$. Moreover, $\boldsymbol{\theta}_{k,l} \triangleq [\theta_{k,l,1}, \dots, \theta_{k,l,M_{\text{path}}^{k,l}}]^T$, $\mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_{k,l}) \triangleq [\mathbf{a}(\theta_{k,l,1}), \dots, \mathbf{a}(\theta_{k,l,M_{\text{path}}^{k,l}})]$, $\boldsymbol{\gamma}_{k,l} \triangleq [\gamma_{k,l,1}, \dots, \gamma_{k,l,M_{\text{path}}^{k,l}}]^T$, $\boldsymbol{\theta}_k \triangleq [\boldsymbol{\theta}_{k,1}^T, \dots, \boldsymbol{\theta}_{k,L_k}^T]^T$, $\mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_k) \triangleq [\mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_{k,1}), \dots, \mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_{k,L_k})]$, and $\boldsymbol{\gamma}_k \triangleq [\boldsymbol{\gamma}_{k,1}^T, \dots, \boldsymbol{\gamma}_{k,L_k}^T]^T$. Without loss of generality, the narrowband channel model of (1) is adopted in this paper for ease of explanations. It is worth mentioning that the development in this paper can be straightforwardly generalized to the more realistic case of wideband channels (as in [16] for massive MIMO and [20] for mmWave MIMO). Stacking all the channel vectors corresponding to K users in a matrix, we obtain

$$\mathbf{H} = [\mathbf{h}_1, \dots, \mathbf{h}_K] = [\mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_1) \boldsymbol{\gamma}_1, \dots, \mathbf{A}(\boldsymbol{\theta}_K) \boldsymbol{\gamma}_K]. \quad (2)$$

Therefore, the received signal by BS can be expressed as

$$\mathbf{Y} = \mathcal{Q}(\mathbf{H}\mathbf{S} + \mathbf{N}) \quad (3)$$

where \mathbf{S} is either the $K \times T_p$ pilot sequence or the $K \times T_d$ data sequence associated with the channel estimation or data detection phases, respectively. \mathbf{N} represents the circularly symmetric complex Gaussian noise sequence with zero mean and covariance matrix $\sigma^2 \mathbf{I}_M$.

B. Binary Classification via GDA

Let a training set contain n training examples $\{\mathbf{x}_j\}_{j=1, \dots, n}$ with z features and their corresponding binary class labels $y_j \in \{1, -1\}_{j=1, \dots, n}$. GDA assumes that the training examples corresponding to the classes -1 and 1 are different realizations of two random vectors normally distributed with different mean vectors $\boldsymbol{\mu}_{-1}$ and $\boldsymbol{\mu}_1$, respectively, and the same covariance matrix $\boldsymbol{\Sigma}$. Thus, respective to y_j and according to the GDA assumptions, the conditional probability density function (PDF) of each \mathbf{x}_j can be modeled as $p(\mathbf{x}_j | y_j = -1) = \mathcal{N}(\boldsymbol{\mu}_{-1}, \boldsymbol{\Sigma})$ and $p(\mathbf{x}_j | y_j = 1) = \mathcal{N}(\boldsymbol{\mu}_1, \boldsymbol{\Sigma})$. The weight vector of the linear decision boundary which separates two classes is then obtained as

$$\mathbf{h}_{\text{GDA}} = \hat{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}}^{-1} (\hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_1 - \hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_{-1}) \quad (4)$$

where $\hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_{-1} = \sum_{j=1}^n \mathbf{1}\{y_j = -1\} \mathbf{x}_j / \sum_{j=1}^n \mathbf{1}\{y_j = -1\}$, $\hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_1 = \sum_{j=1}^n \mathbf{1}\{y_j = 1\} \mathbf{x}_j / \sum_{j=1}^n \mathbf{1}\{y_j = 1\}$, and $\hat{\boldsymbol{\Sigma}} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n (\mathbf{x}_j - \hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_{y_j})(\mathbf{x}_j - \hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_{y_j})^T$ [18].

C. AdaBoost

AdaBoost is an iterative framework designed to build a *strong classifier* using multiple *weak classifiers* [19]. In this framework, any classifier which performs marginally better than random guessing can be considered as a weak classifier. Initially, AdaBoost assigns equal weights to all training examples and trains the first weak classifier. Subsequently, the weights of misclassified training examples are increased at the end of each iteration and the next weak classifier is obtained using the new weighted version of the training data set. Let $h^{(r)}(\mathbf{x})$ and $\mathbf{w}^{(r)} = [w_1^{(r)}, w_2^{(r)}, \dots, w_n^{(r)}]^T$ denote the trained weak classifier and weight vector in the r^{th} iteration, respectively. Moreover, $\epsilon^{(r)} = \sum_{j=1}^n w_j^{(r)} \mathbf{1}(h^{(r)}(\mathbf{x}_j) \neq y_j)$ and $\alpha^{(r)} = \frac{1}{2} \ln \left(\frac{1 - \epsilon^{(r)}}{\epsilon^{(r)} + \delta} \right)$ are respectively the weighted error and the weight of the r^{th} weak classifier. Here, $\delta = 10^{-6}$ is added for numerical stability. Each entry of the weight vector in the $(r+1)^{\text{st}}$ iteration is updated as $w_j^{(r+1)} = w_j^{(r)} \exp(\alpha^{(r)} \mathbf{1}(h^{(r)}(\mathbf{x}_j) \neq y_j))$. Then, the normalization constant $d^{(r+1)} = \sum_{j=1}^n w_j^{(r+1)}$ needs to be computed and each entry of the weight vector be normalized as $w_j^{(r+1)} = \frac{w_j^{(r+1)}}{d^{(r+1)}}$. Finally, the strong classifier which decides the class of a test example \mathbf{x} is constructed as $h_{\text{Ada}}(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{r=1}^R \alpha^{(r)} h^{(r)}(\mathbf{x})$, where R is the number of iterations.

III. PROPOSED ONE-BIT CHANNEL ESTIMATION

For estimating the channel, a pilot sequence $\mathbf{S}_p \in \mathbb{C}^{K \times T_p}$ is used to generate \mathbf{Y}_p as

$$\mathbf{Y}_p = \mathcal{Q}(\mathbf{H}\mathbf{S}_p + \mathbf{N}_p). \quad (5)$$

We can rewrite (2) as

$$\mathbf{H} = [\mathbf{F}\mathbf{g}_1, \dots, \mathbf{F}\mathbf{g}_K] = \mathbf{F}\mathbf{G} \quad (6)$$

where $\mathbf{F} \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times M}$ is the normalized discrete Fourier transform (DFT) matrix and $\mathbf{G} \triangleq [\mathbf{g}_1, \dots, \mathbf{g}_K] \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times K}$. The i^{th} element of \mathbf{g}_k for $k = 1, \dots, K$ can be interpreted as the path gain corresponding to the i^{th} discrete DOA between BS and the k^{th} user. Therefore, \mathbf{g}_k 's can be approximated as sparse vectors. Plugging (6) into (5), we obtain

$$\mathbf{Y}_p = \mathcal{Q}(\mathbf{H}\mathbf{S}_p + \mathbf{N}_p) = \mathcal{Q}(\mathbf{F}\mathbf{G}\mathbf{S}_p + \mathbf{N}_p). \quad (7)$$

Applying the vectorization operator to (7), we get

$$\mathbf{y}_p = \mathcal{Q}((\mathbf{S}_p^T \otimes \mathbf{F}) \mathbf{g} + \mathbf{n}_p) = \mathcal{Q}(\boldsymbol{\Phi}_p \mathbf{g} + \mathbf{n}_p) \quad (8)$$

where $\mathbf{y}_p \triangleq \text{vec}\{\mathbf{Y}_p\}$, $\mathbf{g} \triangleq \text{vec}\{\mathbf{G}\} = [\mathbf{g}_1^T, \mathbf{g}_2^T, \dots, \mathbf{g}_K^T]^T \in \mathbb{C}^{MK}$, $\mathbf{n}_p \triangleq \text{vec}\{\mathbf{N}_p\} \in \mathbb{C}^{MT_p}$, and $\boldsymbol{\Phi}_p \triangleq (\mathbf{S}_p^T \otimes \mathbf{F}) \in \mathbb{C}^{MT_p \times MK}$. For convenience, we convert (8) into the real domain as

$$\bar{\mathbf{y}}_p = \text{sign}(\bar{\boldsymbol{\Phi}}_p \bar{\mathbf{g}} + \bar{\mathbf{n}}_p) \quad (9)$$

where

$$\bar{\mathbf{y}}_p \triangleq [\Re\{\mathbf{y}_p\}^T, \Im\{\mathbf{y}_p\}^T]^T = [\bar{y}_{p,1}, \dots, \bar{y}_{p,2MT_p}]^T \in \{\pm 1\}^{2MT_p} \quad (10a)$$

$$\bar{\Phi}_p \triangleq \begin{bmatrix} \Re\{\Phi_p\} & -\Im\{\Phi_p\} \\ \Im\{\Phi_p\} & \Re\{\Phi_p\} \end{bmatrix} = [\bar{\phi}_{p,1}, \bar{\phi}_{p,2}, \dots, \bar{\phi}_{p,2MT_p}]^T \in \mathbb{R}^{2MT_p \times 2MK} \quad (10b)$$

$$\bar{\mathbf{g}} \triangleq [\Re\{\mathbf{g}\}^T, \Im\{\mathbf{g}\}^T]^T \in \mathbb{R}^{2MK} \quad (10c)$$

$$\bar{\mathbf{n}}_p \triangleq [\Re\{\mathbf{n}_p\}^T, \Im\{\mathbf{n}_p\}^T]^T \in \mathbb{R}^{2MT_p}. \quad (10d)$$

It can be observed from (7), (8), and (10c) that estimating $\bar{\mathbf{g}}$ is equivalent to estimating \mathbf{H} . Furthermore, estimating $\bar{\mathbf{g}}$ in (9) is equivalent to solving a binary classification problem where the training examples, binary class labels, and weight vector of the separating hyperplane are $\{\bar{\phi}_{p,j}\}_{j=1,\dots,2MT_p}$, $\bar{y}_{p,j} \in \{1, -1\}_{j=1,\dots,2MT_p}$, and $\bar{\mathbf{g}}$, respectively. We develop an AdaBoost-based channel estimator that employs a two-stage weak classifier in each iteration. The steps are outlined in Algorithm 1. The number of iterations is denoted by R_p . In the first stage of the r^{th} iteration, we use an approximate GDA binary classification with $\Sigma^{(r)} = \mathbf{I}_{2MK}$ (as in (4)), while a hard thresholding operator is used to enforce sparsity of the vectors \mathbf{g}_k 's in the second stage of each iteration. The first stage in the r^{th} iteration is given as

$$\hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_{-1}^{(r)} = \sum_{j=1}^{2MT_p} \mathbf{1}\{\bar{y}_{p,j} = -1\} w_j^{(r)} \bar{\phi}_{p,j} \quad (11a)$$

$$\hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_{1}^{(r)} = \sum_{j=1}^{2MT_p} \mathbf{1}\{\bar{y}_{p,j} = 1\} w_j^{(r)} \bar{\phi}_{p,j} \quad (11b)$$

$$\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^{(r)} = \hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_{1}^{(r)} - \hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_{-1}^{(r)} \quad (11c)$$

where $\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^{(r)} \in \mathbb{R}^{2MK}$ is the estimate of $\bar{\mathbf{g}}$ in the first stage of the r^{th} iteration. Based on the definition of the matrix \mathbf{G} and its relation with $\bar{\mathbf{g}}$, we construct an estimate of \mathbf{G} in (6) using $\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^{(r)}$ denoted as $\hat{\mathbf{G}}^{(r)} = [\hat{\mathbf{g}}_1^{(r)}, \hat{\mathbf{g}}_2^{(r)}, \dots, \hat{\mathbf{g}}_K^{(r)}] \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times K}$. Here, $\hat{\mathbf{g}}_k^{(r)}$'s are the estimates of \mathbf{g}_k 's in the first stage of the r^{th} iteration. The actual sparsity levels of \mathbf{g}_k 's are unknown. A hard thresholding is introduced as the second stage of the weak classifiers to enforce sparsity of \mathbf{g}_k 's. It consists of applying hard thresholding operator to $\hat{\mathbf{g}}_k^{(r)}$'s in order to cover R_p approximately equispaced sparsity levels from 1 to $\frac{M}{2}$ throughout R_p iterations. These R_p sparsity levels are used as representatives of all possible sparsity levels from 1 to $\frac{M}{2}$ (analogous to [21] and [22]). Moreover, the r^{th} sparsity level is then weighted by $\alpha^{(r)}$ (importance level) in the AdaBoost final step where weak classifiers are combined. This procedure of jointly incrementing the sparsity level and calculating the corresponding significance of that sparsity level in each iteration of the AdaBoost framework enables the proposed method to capture the unknown sparsity level of \mathbf{g}_k 's. To enforce sparsity of \mathbf{g}_k 's, the second stage of the r^{th} iteration is then proposed as

$$\hat{\mathbf{g}}_k^{(r)} = \text{hard}_{t_r} \left(\tilde{\mathbf{g}}_k^{(r)} \right), \quad k = 1, 2, \dots, K \quad (12)$$

where $\text{hard}_{t_r}(\cdot)$ is a hard thresholding operator that preserves only $t_r \triangleq \text{round}\{1 + (r-1)\frac{M-1}{R_p-1}\}$ entries of the bracketed vector argument with the largest absolute value and sets the remaining to 0. We stress here that the hard thresholding stage presented in (12) enables the proposed weak classifiers to capture the sparse structure of \mathbf{g}_k 's by sweeping R_p approximately equispaced sparsity levels from 1 to $\frac{M}{2}$. Capturing the sparse structure of \mathbf{g}_k 's via (12) without knowing the actual sparsity level is an advantage of the proposed channel estimator. It should be noted that instead of $\alpha^{(r)} = \frac{1}{2} \ln\left(\frac{1-\epsilon^{(r)}}{\epsilon^{(r)}+\delta}\right)$ as in the original AdaBoost algorithm [19], we use $\alpha^{(r)} = \frac{1}{4} \ln\left(\frac{1-\epsilon^{(r)}}{\epsilon^{(r)}+\delta}\right)$ in Algorithm 1 as this modification results in better performance.

It should be noted that Algorithm 1 represents a generic framework in the sense that any efficient binary classification can be used in the first stage of the weak classifiers. The motivation for using the approximate GDA binary classification as the first stage of the weak classifiers in this paper is that it is remarkably efficient to implement as it boils down to computing the difference of the weighted mean vectors of the training examples (as in (11a)-(11c)).

Algorithm 1 One-bit Sparse-GDA-AdaBoost Algorithm for Channel Estimation

Input: $\mathcal{S}_p = \{\mathbf{x}_j = \bar{\phi}_{p,j}, y_j = \bar{y}_{p,j}\}_{j=1,\dots,2MT_p}$ whose entries are expressed in (10a) and (10b), \mathbf{F} , and number of iterations R_p .

Output: $\hat{\mathbf{H}}$.

Initialize weights $w_j^{(1)} = \frac{1}{2MT_p}$ for $j \in \{1, 2, \dots, 2MT_p\}$ **for** $r = 1$ to R_p **do**

Use the training set \mathcal{S}_p to compute $\hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_{-1}^{(r)}$, $\hat{\boldsymbol{\mu}}_{1}^{(r)}$, and $\tilde{\mathbf{g}}^{(r)}$ using (11a)-(11c). Then, construct $\hat{\mathbf{G}}^{(r)}$ and use (12) to obtain $\hat{\mathbf{g}}_k^{(r)}$ for $k = 1, 2, \dots, K$.

Construct $\hat{\mathbf{G}}^{(r)} = [\hat{\mathbf{g}}_1^{(r)}, \dots, \hat{\mathbf{g}}_K^{(r)}]$ and $\hat{\mathbf{g}}^{(r)} = [\Re\{\text{vec}\{\hat{\mathbf{G}}^{(r)}\}\}^T, \Im\{\text{vec}\{\hat{\mathbf{G}}^{(r)}\}\}^T]^T$.

Compute error as

$$\epsilon^{(r)} = \sum_{j=1}^{2MT_p} w_j^{(r)} \mathbf{1}(\text{sign}((\bar{\phi}_{p,j})^T \hat{\mathbf{g}}^{(r)}) \neq y_j).$$

Compute $\alpha^{(r)} = \frac{1}{4} \ln\left(\frac{1-\epsilon^{(r)}}{\epsilon^{(r)}+\delta}\right)$ where $\delta = 10^{-6}$ is added for numerical stability.

Update

$$w_j^{(r+1)} = w_j^{(r)} \exp(\alpha^{(r)} \mathbf{1}(\text{sign}((\bar{\phi}_{p,j})^T \hat{\mathbf{g}}^{(r)}) \neq y_j)), \forall j.$$

Compute $d^{(r+1)} = \sum_{j=1}^{2MT_p} w_j^{(r+1)}$ and normalize weights

$$\text{as } w_j^{(r+1)} = \frac{w_j^{(r+1)}}{d^{(r+1)}}, \forall j.$$

end for

Construct $\hat{\mathbf{g}} = \sum_{r=1}^{R_p} \alpha^{(r)} \hat{\mathbf{g}}^{(r)}$, and then normalize as $\hat{\mathbf{g}}_{\text{norm}} = \frac{\sqrt{MK} \hat{\mathbf{g}}}{\|\hat{\mathbf{g}}\|_2}$.

Construct $\hat{\mathbf{G}}$ using $\hat{\mathbf{g}}_{\text{norm}}$ and obtain $\hat{\mathbf{H}} = \mathbf{F} \hat{\mathbf{G}}$.

IV. NUMERICAL EXAMPLES

In this section, we present numerical results to compare the performance of the proposed channel estimator to that of the SVM-based channel estimator [13]. We set the number of weak classifiers $R_p = 10$ for the proposed method and

Fig. 1: NMSE comparison between SVM and the proposed AdaBoost-based channel estimator with $M = 64$, $K = 8$, $L_k = 2$, cluster angle spreads $\in \{8, 10\}$ degrees for all users, and $T_p \in \{10, 20, 40, 80\}$.

Fig. 2: NMSE comparison between SVM and the proposed AdaBoost-based channel estimator with $M = 128$, $K = 8$, $L_k = 4$, cluster angle spreads $\in \{8, 10, 7, 9\}$ degrees for all users, and $T_p \in \{10, 20, 40, 80\}$.

$C = 1$ for the SVM method. Analogous to [13], the m^{th} row of the pilot matrix \mathbf{S}_p is selected to be the $(m + 1)^{\text{th}}$ column of the DFT matrix of size $T_p \times T_p$. The signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) and normalized mean squared error (NMSE) are respectively defined as $\text{SNR} \triangleq 10 \log_{10}(\frac{\|\mathbf{H}\mathbf{S}_p\|_F^2}{MT_p\sigma^2})$ and $\text{NMSE} \triangleq \frac{1}{KN} \sum_{k=1}^K \sum_{n=1}^N \|\frac{\hat{\mathbf{h}}_k^{(n)}}{\|\hat{\mathbf{h}}_k^{(n)}\|_2} - \frac{\mathbf{h}_k}{\|\mathbf{h}_k\|_2}\|_2^2$, where $\hat{\mathbf{h}}_k^{(n)}$ denotes the k^{th} column of $\hat{\mathbf{H}}$ in the n^{th} Monte Carlo trial and N is the total number of Monte Carlo trials, which we set as $N = 1000$. The numbers of channel clusters and within cluster multipaths are set to be the same for all users, i.e., $L_1 = \dots = L_K$ and $M_{\text{path}}^{1,1} = \dots = M_{\text{path}}^{1,L_1} = \dots = M_{\text{path}}^{K,1} = \dots = M_{\text{path}}^{K,L_K} = 10$. The channel path gains are distributed as $\mathcal{CN}(0, 1)$. We generate DOAs once and use them throughout all Monte Carlo trials.

Fig. 1 presents the NMSE comparison between the SVM-based channel estimator and the proposed AdaBoost-based channel estimator for different values of T_p . It can be seen that the performance of the proposed method is remarkably better than that of the SVM-based method for all four values of T_p considered. Particularly, at high SNRs, the proposed method outperforms the SVM method by more than 3 and 4 dB for the cases of $T_p = 40$ and $T_p = 80$, respectively. In Fig. 2, M and L_k are increased to 128 and 4, respectively. It is observed that the proposed AdaBoost-based method dramatically outperforms the SVM method in this scenario as well. Figs. 1 and 2 demonstrate the robustness and accuracy of the proposed channel estimator in capturing the sparse structure of mmWave channels in the angular domain despite the actual sparsity level being unknown.

The impact of using different R_p on the performance of the proposed channel estimator is shown in Fig. 3. It can be seen that setting $R_p = 1$ is a bad choice as the proposed method fails to estimate the channel with this selection. Furthermore,

Fig. 3: The impact of different R_p on the performance of the proposed AdaBoost-based channel estimator when $M = 128$, $K = 8$, $L_k = 2$, cluster angle spreads $\in \{8, 10\}$ degrees for all users, and $T_p = 80$.

setting $R_p = 20$ offers the best performance, however, the performance difference for the cases of $R_p = 10$ and $R_p = 20$ is marginal. Thus, setting $R_p = 10$ is a reasonable choice to ensure both efficiency and accuracy of the proposed method.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, an AdaBoost-based channel estimator has been developed for one-bit mmWave MIMO systems. The AdaBoost-based channel estimator uses two-stage weak classifiers where the approximate GDA binary classification is employed in the first stage and a sweeping hard thresholding operator is used in the second stage. The proposed channel estimator is robust and accurate in capturing the underlying sparse structure of mmWave channels in the angular domain. The superiority of the proposed channel estimator over the SVM-based method has been shown via numerical results.

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